

ENTREPRENEURIAL SUPPORT SYSTEMS AND THE PERFORMANCE OF AGRO-ALLIED SMES IN NORTH CENTRAL NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study examined the effect of entrepreneurial support systems on the performance of agro-allied small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in North Central Nigeria. Adopting a quantitative research approach, the study investigated the relationship between entrepreneurial support systems and SME performance using primary data collected through structured questionnaires administered to SME operators and employees. The study covered Benue, Kogi, Kwara, Nasarawa, Plateau, Niger States, and the Federal Capital Territory, a region critical to Nigeria's agricultural value chain. A descriptive survey design was employed, enabling the use of both descriptive and inferential statistics. From a population of 1,492 registered agro-allied SMEs, a sample size of 956 respondents was determined on a state by state basis using Cochran's formula and selected through simple random sampling. Data were analysed using regression techniques, with variables measured on a five-point Likert scale. Findings revealed that entrepreneurial support systems exert a statistically significant negative effect on SME performance ($B = -0.550$, $p < .001$; $\beta = -0.541$), indicating that increased engagement with existing support mechanisms is associated with reduced performance. This suggests inefficiencies, poor coordination, or administrative burdens within current support structures, which may constrain rather than enhance SME outcomes. The study recommends that SME operators adopt a strategic approach to engaging with support institutions, aligning participation with specific business goals. It further highlights the need for policymakers and support providers to redesign interventions to be more context-specific, collaborative, and value-chain oriented to effectively enhance SME performance.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial Support Systems, SME Performance, Entrepreneurial Ecosystem, Business Development Services, North Central Nigeria
Research paper

Introduction

Small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) are widely recognised as engines of economic growth, employment creation, and innovation in both developed and developing economies (World Bank, 2024). In Nigeria, SMEs constitute a significant proportion of business establishments and play a vital role in poverty reduction and regional development. However, despite their importance, many Nigerian SMEs continue to experience low survival rates, weak competitiveness, and limited growth potential. One of the major constraints facing SMEs in developing economies is inadequate access to effective entrepreneurial support systems (Ilemona, *et al.* (2023).

Entrepreneurial support systems refer to institutional and non-institutional mechanisms that provide SMEs with business development services such as training, mentoring, advisory services, incubation, networking opportunities, and access to market information. Recent literature conceptualises these systems as interdependent ecosystem components that enable productive entrepreneurship through coordinated institutional support (Ilemona, *et al.* (2023). ; PIND Foundation. (2022). These support mechanisms help SMEs overcome market failures, capability gaps, and resource constraints. Within the entrepreneurial ecosystem framework, support systems function as connective infrastructure linking entrepreneurs to finance, knowledge, markets, and policy institutions (Ilemona, *et al.* (2023). Recent empirical evidence from Nigeria highlights persistent structural challenges confronting SMEs, including limited access to finance, infrastructure deficits, and weak institutional coordination (FATE Foundation, 2024; Mohammed, A. D., & Kwode, F. (2026). For instance, the State of Entrepreneurship Report indicates a decline in Nigeria's entrepreneurial performance index from 0.58 in 2022 to 0.46 in 2024, reflecting worsening conditions for SME growth and sustainability (FATE Foundation, 2024).

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While Nigeria has implemented various SME support initiatives through government agencies, development partners, and private-sector organisations, evidence regarding their effectiveness in enhancing SME performance remains mixed and underexplored, particularly at the sub-national level (Ilemona, *et al.* (2023). This study addresses this gap by examining the effect of entrepreneurial support systems on agro-allied SME performance in North Central Nigeria. By focusing on this region, the study provides empirical insights into how support mechanisms influence agro-allied SME outcomes in a context characterised by infrastructural challenges, limited industrial clusters, and uneven institutional support. The objective of this study is to examine the effect of entrepreneurial support systems on the performance of agro-allied SMEs in North Central Nigeria.

H1: Entrepreneurial support systems have a positive and significant effect on the performance of SMEs in North Central Nigeria.

Literature Review

Concept of Entrepreneurial Support Systems

Entrepreneurial support systems comprise a wide spectrum of formal and informal mechanisms aimed at strengthening entrepreneurial capacity and improving firm level performance. These systems include structured interventions such as business training programmes, mentorship and coaching, incubation and acceleration initiatives, consultancy and advisory services, networking platforms, and institutional backing provided by government agencies, development partners, and private-sector organisations (Isenberg, 2010; OECD, 2017). Within the entrepreneurial ecosystem framework, such support mechanisms serve as enabling infrastructure that connects entrepreneurs to critical resources, including knowledge, finance, technology, and markets, thereby enhancing enterprise competitiveness and resilience.

In developing economies, the relevance of entrepreneurial support systems is even more pronounced due to structural constraints such as weak institutions, limited access to finance, inadequate infrastructure, and fragmented markets. SMEs in these contexts often face significant capability gaps and information asymmetries that hinder growth and innovation. Effective support systems mitigate these challenges by strengthening managerial and technical competencies, facilitating access to external expertise, and promoting market integration (Stam, 2015). Through structured learning and relational networks, SMEs are better positioned to adapt to environmental uncertainties and leverage emerging opportunities. Moreover, well-functioning support systems contribute to broader economic development by fostering innovation diffusion, encouraging collaboration, and promoting sustainable enterprise growth. By embedding SMEs within supportive networks of actors and institutions, entrepreneurial support systems enhance firms' absorptive capacity and strategic agility. In contexts characterised by institutional volatility and resource scarcity, the quality, accessibility, and coordination of these support mechanisms largely determine whether SMEs can transition from subsistence-oriented operations to growth-oriented and innovation-driven enterprises.

Entrepreneurial Support Systems and SME Performance

Empirical studies suggest that entrepreneurial support systems positively influence SME performance by improving managerial efficiency, innovation capacity, and strategic decision-making. Business development services such as training and mentoring enhance entrepreneurs' skills, while networking platforms facilitate access to markets, suppliers, and investors (Acs *et al.*, 2014; OECD, 2017). Evidence from developing economies indicates that SMEs that actively engage with support institutions tend to achieve higher growth rates, better financial performance, and greater innovation output than unsupported firms (World Bank, 2022). However, the effectiveness of support systems depends on their accessibility, relevance, and alignment with SME needs. In Nigeria, challenges such as bureaucratic inefficiencies, limited coverage, and weak coordination among support providers have constrained the impact of SME support programmes (World Bank, 2022).

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored in Entrepreneurial Ecosystem Theory and Network Theory, which together provide a robust explanation of how entrepreneurial support systems influence Agro-allied SME performance. Entrepreneurial Ecosystem Theory, advanced by scholars such as Isenberg (2010), Stam (2015), and further developed by Acs *et al.* (2014), posits that entrepreneurship thrives within a system of interdependent actors and institutional arrangements, including government, finance, culture, human capital, markets, and support organisations. The core tenet of the theory is that firm performance is not solely a function of individual entrepreneurial ability but of the quality and coherence of the surrounding ecosystem. Within this framework, entrepreneurial support systems such as incubators, accelerators, business development services, mentorship programmes, and policy support mechanisms constitute critical ecosystem pillars that reduce institutional voids, enhance capability development, and facilitate access to strategic resources. Thus, support systems operate as enabling infrastructures that strengthen opportunity recognition, innovation capacity, and overall SME performance by fostering coordination among ecosystem actors.

Network Theory, rooted in the works of Granovetter (1973) on the strength of weak ties and further elaborated in social capital literature, emphasises that economic actions are embedded in social relationships. Its central proposition is that access to information, resources, and opportunities is largely determined by the structure and quality of relational ties. In the context of entrepreneurial support systems, Network Theory explains how mentorship platforms, professional associations, incubators, and cluster initiatives enhance SMEs' network embeddedness and social capital.

By connecting entrepreneurs to suppliers, customers, investors, research institutions, and government agencies, support systems expand both strong and weak ties, thereby improving knowledge flows, resource mobilisation, and market access. Consequently, entrepreneurial support systems function not only as service providers but also as network brokers that strengthen relational linkages, reduce information asymmetry, and enhance SME competitiveness and performance.

Fig 2.1 Conceptual Framework
Source: Author (2026)

Methodology

This research utilised a quantitative research design to study the relationship between entrepreneurial support systems and the performance of agro-allied small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) in North Central Nigeria. Primary data were collected through a structured survey administered to agro-allied SMEs operators and employees, providing firsthand quantitative data into how entrepreneurial support systems affect the performance of agro-allied SMEs. The study area is North Central Nigeria, covering Benue, Kogi, Kwara, Nasarawa, Plateau, Niger States, and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). The region is agriculturally rich and plays a strategic role in Nigeria's food production, with agro-allied SMEs forming a significant part of the agricultural value chain. A descriptive survey method was engaged to collect data at a single point in time. This method enabled the use of descriptive and inferential statistics to analyse relationships between entrepreneurial support systems and agro-allied SMEs performance. Structured questionnaires were used as the primary data collection instrument, ensuring objectivity, reliability, generalisability, and cost-effectiveness. The primary data were sourced through online questionnaire (Google Forms) administered to agro-allied SMEs operators and employees across both urban and rural areas. Data collection was made possible with the assistance of state managers of the Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN) across the study area, which improved accessibility and response rates. The unit of analysis comprised individual SMEs operators and employees, selected because of their direct involvement and firsthand knowledge of enterprise operations and performance.

The study population consisted of 1,492 registered agro-allied SMEs in North Central Nigeria, as obtained from (SMEDAN, 2021). Using Cochran's (1977) sample size determination formula at a 95% confidence level and 5% margin of error, a total sample size of 956 respondents was derived and proportionately distributed across the six States and the FCT. Simple random sampling was employed to ensure equal selection probability, minimise bias, and enhance the representativeness of the sample. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire divided into two sections. Section A captured respondents' socio-demographic characteristics, while Section B comprised (7) 5 Likert-scale items measuring entrepreneurial support system and agro-allied SME performance. Competitive advantage was adopted as a key non-financial indicator of SME performance. Reactions were measured on a five-point Likert scale ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree." Ethical considerations were strictly observed. Contribution was deliberate, respondents were informed of the study's purpose, confidentiality was assured, and no inducements were offered.

Results

Result of the study is stated below both in descriptive and inferential statistics. This revealed the distinctive attributes of the study in frequency and percentage for meaningful assimilation of the data used in the study.

Demographic Analysis

The demographic analysis provided critical background information on respondents, offered context for interpreting the study's findings on agro-allied SMEs in North Central Nigeria. The analysis covered key characteristics, including state of business operation, respondent status within enterprises, years of business experience, age, and educational qualifications. These variables, while not part of the study's control objectives, helped contextualize patterns that may influence SMEs performance.

Table 1 Demographic Table

Variable	Category	Frequency
State of Business Operation	Federal Capital Territory (FCT)	114
	Nasarawa State	106
	Niger State	85
	Benue State	116
	Kogi State	103
	Kwara State	94
	Plateau State	95
	Total	713
Status of Respondents	Farm Operator	544
	Farm Employee	169
	Total	713
Years of Business Operation	Less than 1 year	126
	1–5 years	141
	5–10 years	133
	10–15 years	212
	15 years and above	101
	Total	713
Age of Respondents	Less than 20 years	9
	20–30 years	162
	30–40 years	199
	40–50 years	197
	50–60 years	119
	60 years and above	27
	Total	713
Education Qualification	First School Leaving Certificate	12
	WASC/GCE/NECO Certificate	211
	OND/NCE/Diploma Certificate	313
	HND/BSc/BA Certificate	171
	PGD/MSc/MA/PhD Certificate	6
	Total	713

Source:
Author's
Computation

The distribution of agro-allied SMEs in North Central Nigeria and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) shows a fairly balanced geographical spread, with Benue State (16.3%) and the FCT (16.0%) having the highest concentrations, while Niger State (11.9%) recorded the lowest. Most respondents are farm operators (76.3%), with employees making up 23.7%, indicating that the dataset primarily reflects insights from decision-makers responsible for strategic and operational management. The years of business operation vary, with 29.7% of SMEs having operated for 10-15 years, demonstrating resilience, and 37.5% in operation for less than five years, reflecting active entry of new ventures. This combination of experienced and emerging enterprises provides a balanced view of the challenges and opportunities across different growth stages.

The age distribution reveals that the majority of respondents are within the productive age brackets of 30-40 years (27.9%) and 40-50 years (27.6%), highlighting the dominance of middle-aged entrepreneurs in driving SME performance, with limited involvement from younger (<20 years) or older (60+ years) individuals. Educational qualifications indicate a relatively well-educated workforce, with 43.9% holding OND/NCE/Diploma certificates and 24% possessing university degrees, while only 1.7% have primary education. This profile suggests that agro-allied SMEs benefit from skilled and knowledgeable operators and employees, which can enhance innovation, adoption of modern farming practices, and overall enterprise performance.

Construct Analysis

The construct analysis focused on examining the key variables of the study as measured by the survey instrument. It presented respondents' perceptions and evaluations of entrepreneurial support system and its relationship to the performance of agro-allied SMEs in North Central Nigeria. Using descriptive statistics such as frequencies and percentages, this section highlights the distribution of responses across each construct. The analysis provided insight into how the respondents viewed the enabling environment for agro-allied SMEs operations and established the basis for subsequent inferential testing of the hypothesised relationships between the entrepreneurial support system and agro-allied SMEs performance.

Table 2. Entrepreneurial Support System

Statement	Response	Frequency	Percentage
(1) Business mentoring programmes have positively contributed to our success.	Strongly Disagree	272	38.1
	Disagree	306	42.9
	Neutral	5	0.7
	Agree	16	2.2
	Strongly Agree	114	16.0
	Total	713	100.0
(2) We have access to business incubators or accelerators.	Strongly Disagree	336	47.1
	Disagree	316	44.3
	Neutral	3	0.4
	Agree	0	0.0
	Strongly Agree	58	8.1
	Total	713	100.0
(3) There are support services available to help navigate government regulations.	Strongly Disagree	177	24.8
	Disagree	475	66.6
	Neutral	3	0.4
	Agree	0	0.0
	Strongly agree	58	8.1
	Total	713	100.0
(4) Support organisations provide practical assistance to SMEs.	Strongly Disagree	329	46.1
	Disagree	322	45.2
	Neutral	4	0.6
	Agree	0	0.0
	Strongly Agree	58	8.1
	Total	713	100.0

(5) We receive helpful guidance from SME development agencies or organisations.

Strongly Disagree	365	51.2
Disagree	286	40.1
Neutral	4	0.6
Agree	0	0.0
Strongly Agree	58	8.1
Total	713	100.0

(6) Networking opportunities provided by support systems benefit our business.

Strongly Disagree	331	46.4
Disagree	323	45.3
Neutral	1	0.1
Agree	0	0.0
Strongly Agree	58	8.1
Total	713	100.0

(7) The business environment in my area facilitates SME growth.

Strongly Disagree	261	36.6
Disagree	390	54.7
Neutral	4	0.6
Agree	0	0.0
Strongly Agree	58	8.1
Total	713	100.0

Source: Author’s Computation (2026)

The table reveals an overwhelmingly negative perception of entrepreneurial support systems and the broader business environment among the 713 SME respondents. For Statement 1, 81.0% (38.1% strongly disagree; 42.9% disagree) indicated that business mentoring programmes have not positively contributed to their success, with only 18.2% expressing agreement (2.2% agree; 16.0% strongly agree). Similarly, access to business incubators or accelerators (Statement 2) appears extremely limited, as 91.4% of respondents disagreed or strongly disagreed, and none selected “Agree.” This suggests that formal incubation and acceleration structures are either inaccessible or ineffective within the study context.

Statements 3 to 6 further reinforce this pattern. Between 90% and 92% of respondents disagreed that support services help them navigate regulations, that support organisations provide practical assistance that SME development agencies offer helpful guidance, or that networking opportunities benefit their businesses. Notably, “Agree” responses are virtually absent across these items, while a consistent 8.1% selected “Strongly Agree,” suggesting that benefits from support systems may be concentrated among a small subset of firms. Finally, 91.3% of respondents disagreed that the business environment facilitates SME growth (Statement 7), indicating a structurally unsupportive ecosystem. Overall, the descriptive statistics point to weak institutional support, limited access to structured assistance, and a constrained entrepreneurial ecosystem, which may significantly hinder SME growth and performance in the study area.

Measurement Model

The measurement model demonstrated acceptable levels of composite reliability and convergent validity, indicating that the constructs were measured reliably.

Source: Author’s
Computation (2026)

The figure presented the structural model examining the effect of Support System (SS) on SMEs Performance (SP). The path coefficient ($\beta = -0.597$) indicated a strong negative relationship, suggesting that weaknesses or inefficiencies in support systems are associated with lower SMEs performance in the study context. The R^2 value of 0.357 shows that support systems explain 35.7% of the variance in SME performance, indicating moderate explanatory power in line with acceptable thresholds in PLS-SEM research (Hair *et al.*, 2022). Regarding the measurement model, most support system indicators (SS2-SS7) demonstrate strong loadings (0.899-0.929), exceeding the recommended 0.70 benchmark and confirming indicator reliability and convergent validity. SS1, with a loading of 0.667, falls slightly below the 0.70 threshold but may be retained in exploratory research if composite reliability and AVE remain acceptable (Hair *et al.*, 2022).

The deletion of SP1, SP2, and SP3 is methodologically justified if their factor loadings were below 0.70 or if they reduced composite reliability (CR) and average variance extracted (AVE). SEM literature strongly recommends removing weak indicators to enhance construct reliability, internal consistency, and convergent validity, particularly when such items inflate measurement error and weaken structural estimates (Hair *et al.*, 2022; Henseler *et al.*, 2015). Retaining poorly loading items can bias path coefficients and reduce the predictive accuracy of the model (Sarstedt *et al.*, 2021). Therefore, eliminating SP1-SP3 improves the psychometric robustness of the SMEs performance construct, ensuring that the retained items (SP4-SP7), with loadings between 0.623 and 0.882, more accurately capture the latent performance dimension. This refinement strengthens the validity of the structural relationship observed between support systems and SMEs performance.

Table 3 Regression Hypothesis Result

Predictor	B	SE B	B	T	p	95% CI for B
Constant	5.209	0.068	-	77.052	< .001	[5.077, 5.342]
SS	-0.550	0.032	-0.541	-17.155	< .001	[-0.613, -0.487]

Source: Author's Computation (2026)

The regression results indicate that support systems (SS) have a statistically significant negative effect on SME performance. The unstandardized coefficient ($B = -0.550$, $p < .001$) implies that a one-unit increase in SS is associated with a 0.55-unit decrease in SME performance, holding other factors constant. The 95% confidence interval for this estimate [-0.613, -0.487] excludes zero, confirming the stability and reliability of the effect. Therefore, the above proposed alternate hypothesis is rejected. The standardized coefficient ($\beta = -0.541$) suggests a strong negative relationship, indicating that support systems explain a substantial proportion of the variation in SME performance within the model. The large absolute t -value (-17.155) further reinforces the strength of this relationship. Substantively, this result suggests that existing support mechanisms such as government agencies, business development services, or institutional intermediaries may be ineffective, poorly coordinated, or burdensome, thereby constraining rather than enhancing SME performance in the study.

Discussion

The regression revealed a statistically significant and strong negative relationship between entrepreneurial support systems and SME performance ($B = -0.550$, $\beta = -0.541$, $p < .001$). This result is both empirically robust and substantively important, given the narrow confidence interval and large t -value. Contrary to dominant empirical evidence that positions support systems as performance enhancers (World Bank, 2022), the result suggests that, within the context of agro-allied SMEs in North Central Nigeria, existing institutional support mechanisms may be counterproductive. Rather than strengthening managerial capacity or innovation outcomes, engagement with support institutions appears associated with reduced performance.

Several contextual explanations may account for this divergence from prior studies. In Nigeria, SME support programmes are often characterised by bureaucratic bottlenecks, limited rural accessibility, weak inter-agency coordination, and policy inconsistency. Agro-allied SMEs, particularly those operating in semi-urban and rural areas, may face administrative delays, compliance costs, or politically influenced selection processes when attempting to access government-backed support schemes. Such inefficiencies can increase transaction costs and divert managerial time and resources away from core operational activities. Furthermore, support programmes may be too generic, failing to address sector-specific constraints such as post-harvest technology, agro-processing infrastructure, supply chain logistics, and value-chain financing. Where support is poorly aligned with enterprise needs, it may generate minimal productivity gains or even disrupt business focus.

Another possible explanation is reverse causality: underperforming SMEs may be more likely to seek institutional support, meaning that engagement reflects distress rather than strength. In this case, the negative coefficient does not necessarily imply that support systems inherently reduce performance, but rather that firms accessing them are already experiencing operational challenges. Additionally, if support initiatives emphasise compliance reporting or short-term programme participation without sustained mentorship and monitoring, their long-term impact may be limited. The findings highlight a critical policy implication: the existence of support institutions alone does not guarantee improved SME outcomes. Effectiveness depends on accessibility, relevance, coordination, and measurable impact. For agro-allied SMEs in North Central Nigeria, reforming support systems to become more sector-specific, decentralised, transparent, and outcome-driven is essential to reversing the negative association and transforming institutional support into a genuine driver of performance.

Conclusion

The findings of this study demonstrate that support systems exert a statistically significant and strong negative effect on the performance of agro-allied SMEs in North Central Nigeria. Contrary to prevailing empirical literature that portrays entrepreneurial support mechanisms as catalysts for growth, innovation, and managerial efficiency, the results indicate that existing institutional arrangements may be constraining rather than enhancing enterprise outcomes. This suggests that the mere presence of support agencies, business development services, or government-backed programmes does not automatically translate into improved SME performance. Instead, structural inefficiencies, bureaucratic burdens, weak coordination, and possible misalignment between programme design and sector-specific needs may undermine their effectiveness.

The results therefore underscore a critical contextual reality: institutional support must be functional, accessible, and strategically aligned with enterprise challenges to produce measurable performance gains. In the absence of such alignment, support mechanisms may increase transaction costs, divert managerial focus, or attract firms already experiencing operational distress, thereby reinforcing weak performance outcomes. The study thus challenges conventional assumptions and calls for a re-evaluation of how SME support systems are structured and implemented within the agro-allied sector in North Central Nigeria.

Policy Implications

The findings suggest the urgent need to reform and restructure SME support frameworks to ensure efficiency, coordination, and sector-specific relevance. Policymakers should prioritise decentralising support services to rural and semi-urban areas, simplifying administrative procedures, and reducing bureaucratic bottlenecks that discourage effective participation. Greater integration among government agencies, financial institutions, research bodies, and private-sector actors is essential to avoid duplication and fragmentation of support initiatives. Additionally, monitoring and evaluation systems should shift from output-based metrics to outcome-based indicators that measure productivity, innovation, and competitiveness improvements.

Practical Implication

Agro-allied SMEs operators should approach institutional support strategically, carefully evaluating the cost benefit implications of programme participation. Engagement with support institutions should be aligned with clearly defined business objectives, particularly in areas such as technology upgrading, managerial training, and market expansion. Support providers, on their part, must design customised advisory and mentoring services tailored to agro-allied value chains, including post-harvest management, processing efficiency, logistics optimisation, and product differentiation. Strengthening collaboration between SMEs and universities or agricultural research institutes may also enhance the practical value of support interventions.

Limitations and Future Research

This study is subject to certain limitations. First, SMEs performance was measured primarily using non-financial indicators, which may not fully capture objective financial outcomes such as profitability or return on investment. Second, the cross-sectional design limits the ability to establish long-term causal relationships between support systems and performance. Third, the analysis focused on registered agro-allied SMEs within North Central Nigeria, which may restrict the generalisability of the findings to informal enterprises or other geopolitical zones. Future research could adopt longitudinal designs, incorporate financial performance metrics, and conduct comparative regional analyses to provide deeper insights into the evolving role of support systems in SME development.

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